

THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND ITS NATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation. This article describes in detail the expression of the linguistic landscape of the world in English and Uzbek languages through idioms, the parallel occurrence of lexical and phraseological meanings, and the study of national and cultural characteristics of English and Uzbek idioms.

Key words: combination, linguistic landscape, phrase, lexical meaning, structural unity, explicit form.

Phraseological units present in the language system take an active part in naming things and events, such as words, from a functional point of view, in performing communicative relations. There are a number of phraseological expressions, the concrete or figurative meanings of the words - components involved in their formation are manifested in some implicit, and in others explicit form. They have retained their meaning and form plan as a phrasal component. Such cases are the basis for recognizing the opinions of supporters of the second direction. We observe that the parallel occurrence of lexical and phraseological meanings is also present in a number of phraseological units. As it can be seen from the examples, the phraseological fund of each language contains different expressions according to their formation from the semantic point of view. has preserved its meaning.

In modern linguistics, problems related to the study of the national-cultural specificity of a particular subsystem of the language in a typological sense are particularly relevant. In connection with the expanding contacts between peoples by economic, political, cultural and scientific ties, the need for theoretical research puts these topics in a number of problems. Learning the vocabulary of any language is always an interesting learning process. Learning English vocabulary can be boring or interesting. Just take the words from the dictionary and teach them how a poem alone can be a boring thing, but if you will, learn words in a group with friends, this process will seem very interesting and not very difficult occupation, process. In the context of interactive learning, knowledge takes on different forms. On the one hand, they represent certain

information about the world around them. The peculiarity of this information is that the student receives it not in the form of a ready-made system from the teacher, but in the process of their own activity. The teacher must create situations in which the student is active, in which he asks, acts. As you know, a comparative study of linguistic phenomena accumulates the information necessary for an adequate explanation of the national-specific vision of the world. “Modern linguistic science, which deals with the establishment of language universals of a different nature, is mainly occupied with revealing intersystemic closeness in different structural languages” (2). A feature of the development of modern linguistics is the increased interest in the content side of linguistic phenomena, which is caused by the understanding of language as a system in which all elements of its structure are interconnected and interdependent. Currently, attempts are being made to study vocabulary and phraseology as a structurally organized level, to identify the main types of their lexical and lexical-semantic relations and relations in the language.

In connection with the development of comparative typological works in the field of lexical and phraseological semantics of related and unrelated languages, the national-cultural specificity of the semantics of linguistic units, the establishment of peculiar semantic-stylistic components in the structure of their meaning are of particular relevance. The national-cultural specifics of phraseological units with animal names are determined by linguistic and extralinguistic factors. The linguistic basis of the national-cultural specificity of phraseological units with animal names is made up of the mismatch or partial coincidence of their figurative structures, which in turn is due to the peculiarities of phrase-forming processes that occur when forming the figurative meaning in phraseological units with animal names, where the source of motivation for the figurative meanings of phraseological units with animal names is the figurative meaning of words with animal names. It is well known that the national-cultural specificity in the semantics of the analyzed phraseological units with animal names is determined by linguistic and extralinguistic factors that influence the formation of imagery and its national-cultural specificity. Each language is characterized by national-cultural characteristics, due to the life and development of a particular society, i.e. what makes up its national-cultural specificity. It is comparative typological research that is an effective means of identifying the national-cultural specifics of phraseological units with animal names their semantics, since the task of the comparative typology is to “compare systems of different genetically related and

unrelated languages, identify common and specific features, establish interlanguage correspondences within specific, quantitatively limited languages, taking into account their typical or systemic features” (3,4). National and cultural specificity is evident in varying degrees at all levels of language: phonetic, lexical, phraseological, word-formation, syntax, and units of different language levels have the national-cultural specificity in different degrees. Based on the position that the nature of imagery reflects the national originality of a language picture of the world in different languages (7), and the national peculiarity of phraseological units can be traced in the study of any aspect of her, however, on the semantic level, it is manifested most clearly, we will try to explain the typological model of the Association of imagery, forming the national-cultural specificity of FUNA (phraseological units with the names of animals) in the compared languages. Particularly bright, as the researchers note, national-cultural specificity is evident in the phraseological system of language, which explicitly and directly related to the surrounding reality. National-cultural specificity of semantics of lexical units has recently been given increasing attention both in theoretical and in practical terms, as evidenced by the large number of studies, articles and monographs, the creation of linguistic-cultural dictionaries, manuals (5). Of particular importance in this regard, acquire research to identify and study national and cultural specificity of semantics of lexical units, to define and identify the cultural component values and the establishment of his status in the semantic structure of language units.

It should be emphasized that language is created on the basis of universal laws of perception of the world. Because the logical thinking ability of a person is common, regardless of which corner of the earth they are. If this commonality did not exist, peoples living on different continents and speaking different languages would not understand each other, would not be able to communicate with each other. A clear proof of this is the presence of phraseological units, both in form and meaning, among the fully equivalent lexical units that exist in languages.

As in all languages, we see thousands of idioms among the lexical units of the English vocabulary. These units have been sealing the national-cultural way of life and social development of the British people for centuries. In the course of our research, we found it necessary to focus on a number of features of phrases. Phraseological units present in the language system take an active part in naming things and events, such as words, from a functional point of view, in performing communicative relations. Every language has a phraseological

system, its units are constantly used as words to increase the vocabulary of the language, to name objects and events, and in the process of daily communication. In such language units, the national-cultural identity, traditions, mentality, and history of peoples are sealed for life.

The people create units that are short in form but have a deep expressive meaning in order to name and express new concepts, to realize different social situations, or to reveal different aspects of existing concepts and realities. These are, of course, expressions that have passed through many years of experience of that nation, and are understandable for that nation, people, and people. These phraseological units usually not only simply name something, but also assess its connotative (stylistic) coloring, the speaker's attitude to existence, and therefore the phraseological meaning is a specific meaning in the language.

Phrases are unique language elements in expressing the linguistic landscape of the world. Their phraseological meaning structure contains not only linguistic information, but also extralinguistic information. Each nation creates phraseological units with deep expressive meaning in order to name new concepts, express them, and realize various social situations.

Phrasemes are also unique as a language unit that expresses the national-cultural characteristics of each nation. Cross-sectional study of the phrasemes of the English and Uzbek peoples, who belong to different language systems, are located geographically far from each other, and have not directly entered into various social, political, and religious relations. showed that there are a number of allomorphic and isomorphic features between them.

Particular attention is paid to the study of phraseological units as unique examples, conducting comparative-comparison, classification, descriptive research, and at the same time, to the identification of isomorphic and allomorphic features in the semantics of English and Uzbek phraseological units. In conclusion, it should be said that by studying the national and cultural features of the English and Uzbek phrases, it is possible to show that people's ability to think logically, regardless of where they live and what language they speak, have a common logical commonality, both in terms of form and meaning. plan can also be seen by comparing English and Uzbek language paremies in the example of the analysis of fully equivalent phrases.

The close connection of English phrases with the European culture and development and the commonality with the names of the heroes of ancient mythological literature show their differences from the Uzbek language. One of the distinctive features of English idioms is that eponymous idioms are

represented by personal names and related objects. Phrases related to ancient heroes are very rare in the Uzbek language stock of phrases.

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